

SMART LIFESTYLE AND SPIRITUALITY OF YOUTH

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ANNOTATION

In the article, the basic principles of the idea of national independence, the importance of human, especially youth problems in the correct understanding and understanding of a reasonable national way of life, "Today we are building a new state, a new society, this is a system of socio-political relations, people, it is especially emphasized that consciousness and the thinking of young people is unique, and at the same time it takes on a whole new meaning. It talks about the way of life of people, our youth and their views on it, radically changing as a result of the passage of time, in the case of several nations, the recognition of spiritual satisfaction and spiritual stability in a person.

Key words: national, independence, idea, principle, education, generation, youth, society, indigenous, essence, rise, change, life, reasonable, work, nationality, nation, interest, method, conditions, ancient, history, soil.

The main principles of the idea of national independence make the problems related to youth more relevant in understanding the national way of life. "Today, as we are building a new state, a new society, in this system socio-political relations, the consciousness and thinking of people and young people will undoubtedly acquire a new meaning. First of all, the relationship between the individual and the state, and between the person and the society must find a completely new meaning and form, be based on new characteristics, new principles. In other words, all these should be relations that are compatible with the essence

of new values and democratic principles, our way of life and way of thinking, and meet the requirements of the just society we are building."

The above points give a conceptual conclusion that the new criteria, principles of living, the vitality of the national ideology, which are established in our society today, should be able to embody the nature of our national way of life and be compatible with its spirit. On the other hand, a lifestyle is not just a set of some living principles, but also a complex process that always requires internal laws, contradictions and the interaction of poles. Because of this, any needs and principles that are formed are tested, perfected or, on the contrary, denied in this field.

Therefore, understanding the way of life as a dialectical process leads to the correct definition of its nature and essence. The national way of life reflects the economic, local-territorial organization, spiritual world and self-realization of the nation at a certain stage of social development, its unique life, its colorful forms, social development activity, which is different from other nationalities.

The process of deepening and enriching the national lifestyle is connected with objective social factors. Among them, the creation of decent living conditions, especially in the social life of young people, has a special place. As the main criterion of the ideology of national independence, the idea of independence in the Strategy of Actions is to build a free and prosperous Motherland, a free and prosperous life, and it is self-evident that the main task is to fundamentally renew the living standards of the people, to ensure a beautiful and prosperous life. Therefore, today, concepts such as the unique role of youth in prosperity and well-being have become the main criteria of our national policy. For this purpose, major socio-economic activities are being carried out, such as strengthening the material and technical base of national life, expropriation of property, deepening privatization processes, implementation of structural changes, wide involvement of foreign investments in production, and application of advanced technologies.¹

In the field of social strengthening of our national way of life, much attention is paid to raising the country's national income. In particular, the issue of state aid to low-income sections of the society, in need of social protection, is not being positively resolved. Legal guarantees of the national way of life are getting stronger.

Determining the national nature of a lifestyle is associated with a number of problems. In the scientific literature, especially in the works published during the Soviet period, a lot was written about the nationalistic elements of the lifestyle. In fact, some aspects of nationality were artificially attached to the phenomenon of lifestyle, which is considered to be essentially a national phenomenon, opinions were expressed only from the official side about the existence of national symbols in the abstract Soviet-socialist lifestyle, and the main attention was paid to the process of internationalization, and nationality was officially recorded. As a result, this thing has led to the destruction of the lifestyle of our people, especially among the youth, in particular, their life goals, way of thinking, and social character.²

When thinking about the national content of the lifestyle, or the national lifestyle in general, in our opinion, it is necessary to clarify the content of such concepts as "lifestyle" and "national stylistics of behavior" that are typical for specific units of a certain social structure and strata divided by age. Of course, these concepts assume that the behavior of representatives of a particular nation, ethnic group takes place in the historical background, specific programs, rules and socially significant "patterns" of life. Here, of course, we are talking about people's lives, it can be said about the national style of the growing young generation, mature generation.

"Life style" represents the geographical, natural conditioned forms of life activity, historical national traditions, and socio-psychological patterns of behavior, and reflects the way of life that was practically tested by the nation in the past or preserved to this day.

Research shows that this is also a way of thinking. This is evidenced by the results of sociological research conducted on the identification of sociocultural characteristics of the

way of thinking in the process of democratization of society in Uzbekistan. ³ This reflects the unique style of thinking and its essence. For the analysis, 8 types of thinking and their related subgroups are selected, and the result is determined as follows.

According to the researches of sociologist B. Farfiev, it is possible to be sure that the pragmatic way of thinking is the priority. It is understood that personal and social problems are gaining pragmatic importance during the transition to free market relations. Among intellectuals and students, the second indicator is mainly scientific thinking. The reason that thinking from the point of view of the public interest is in the third place among intellectuals, students, merchants, and in the second place among the peasants and workers is that concern for the public interest is at the level of the previous demand in all the studied social groups. In our opinion, it would be correct to say that this is the "predominance of the spirit of living as a community in the life of our people from time immemorial."

Among the people of villages, not to sit with one's head in front of the elderly has been preserved as an ancient rule of etiquette. Also, people wear caps on ordinary days and holidays, especially on days of mourning. There is a special way of greeting for our people. It is customary to ask the elders by shaking both hands, bowing the head and putting a hand on the chest when meeting people. It is known that there is a certain consistency in the mutual greetings of women.

Of course, spiritual culture plays a special role in ensuring the manifestation and uniqueness of the national way of life. By the way, the national culture, which summarizes the material and spiritual values of the nation and contains the practical and creative activities, experiences, knowledge and skills of people, becomes the norm of behavior, communication and relations. Although the culture of the peoples has not been historically isolated, each of them has its own path of development and has formed as a national phenomenon. Therefore, national forms of culture have become traditions and have had a significant impact on the way of life as a stable, integrated phenomenon.

By its nature, lifestyle or manner can be said to be one of the materialized aspects of traditional culture, so it is not difficult to understand that even today it continues to have its influence on various forms of life activity. In other words, national culture, including national traditions, is one of the important determinants of the manifestation and creation of a national lifestyle. However, the relationship between national lifestyle and culture is not directly manifested. This means that culture, as a spiritual phenomenon, is not among the structural elements of the national lifestyle, but actively participates in the formation and development of its specific elements in a wide spatial and contemporary framework. The role of traditional culture in illuminating the nature of the national way of life can be properly understood on this basis.

As the researchers rightly noted, the elements of national identity of the lifestyle, the aspects embodying its national nature, are implemented by cultural functions that socially regulate people's everyday life. According to Q. Khonazarov, active aspects of national culture, life, traditions and customs are components of lifestyle.⁴

We can see that the national aspects of the way of life are connected with the traditional culture to a certain extent in the examples of folk oral creativity, written sources, and the first monuments of fiction, which are the ancient monuments of the religious and secular lifestyle of our people.

The tradition of Zoroastrian rituals occupies a special place in the lifestyle of the Uzbek people. Researcher A. Ashirov writes that "after Zoroastrian religion, i.e. belief in one God, was officially accepted, the practice of "sydraposh" was introduced. According to this, it is customary for a Zoroastrian who fully fulfills Ahuramazda's duties and the sunnahs of Zoroastrian teachings, who is pure in all respects, has high morals, who has received the blessing of the teacher, to wear a white cloth robe and shirt, wrap a turban on his head, and tie a belt made of woolen thread around his waist... In our opinion, our people The rites related to wearing a robe and tying a belt between them are probably a transformed form of the Zoroastrian "sidraposhlik" ceremony.⁵

In fact, the customs of many rituals in Zoroastrianism have been preserved in the lifestyle of our people until now. In this case, it is possible to cite as an example that today's holidays related to farming are in accordance with Zoroastrian traditions. In the spring, there were celebrations such as "Dalaga kosh izrja", "Ekin sali", "Kosh oshi", "Mother wheat", "Harmon wedding", "Harvest holiday" related to sowing seeds on the ground. In Zoroastrianism, holidays such as Navruz and Mehrjan, the emergence of the spring flower, the opening of tulips, the blossoming of almonds, and the fact that spring is generally considered to be the celebration of the spirit of goodness, caused great rejoicing. Such customs, typical of the cultural lifestyle of the ancients, are celebrated today in Khorezm and Bukhara in the form of "Kizil gul saili", "Lola saili" in Fergana, Ko'kan and Tashkent suburbs, "Sunbula saili" in Chust, and "Boychechak saili" in other places.⁶

As noted, in "Avesta" the basis of the lifestyle of the ancients was formed by three ethics - good thoughts, good words and good deeds, in which truth, education, training, good and bad, woman, family, marriage, ecological and medical ideas, as well as the economy with goodness issues such as interdependence, property and credit relations, production, labor and division of labor, the role of nature in satisfying needs are described in a unique way?

Uzbeks have a saying that children are brought up not only by parents, but also by relatives, neighbors, and the community. The environment has had a great influence on the formation of the moral image of young people in all times. In families with many children, especially in rural areas, children are used to honest work, to educate their siblings, to help their parents and neighbors from a young age. It is also considered a high moral virtue to greet each other and ask how they are doing when they meet, big or small. The fact that young people go out and help when there is a ceremony in the house of their neighbors is also a result of national education. Girls did not read books about modesty, modesty, modesty, chastity, honor, but learned from their parents and neighbors for the first time.⁷

Thus, national signs of lifestyle are first of all connected with the history of the nation, its culture, language, traditions, customs and other spheres of spiritual life. In the words of

the famous philosopher I. Jabbarov, the dialectical relationship between the past and the present applies here. Therefore, "the memory of the past is one of the important factors for spiritual and cultural development, while the experience accumulated over the centuries is the most necessary ground for the maturation of a person, the historical development of the people and the nation." ⁸ Therefore, nationality is the product of the original essence of the historical experience of the people, its unforgettable and immortal. is social memory.

In short, there is no need to restore the reactionary customs and lifestyles that have lived out their lives in society, both economically and morally. "It is very wrong and dangerous to have a system of relations in the society where the interests of a particular group or particular regions are higher than the common interests. Elevating specific territorial differences to the level of an absolute phenomenon is the most dangerous mistake. Each person's return to national identity should not be determined by their regional sense of identity. First of all, a person should feel that he is a citizen of Uzbekistan. This situation does not reduce the value and importance of the homeland, the place where a person was born and raised, its lifestyle and unique values.

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